

A New Synthesis of Derivatives of Benztriazole.

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Under the definition of benztriazoles are included those compounds which were formerly obtained by the action of nitrous acid on aromatic *o*-diamines, the first of which was prepared by Hoffmann (*Annalen*, 1860, **115**, 251) from *o*-diamino-nitrobenzene, and which was definitely proved by Griess (*Ber.*, 1882, **15**, 1878) to have the constitution (I). Subsequently Ullmann and Mauthner (*Ber.*, 1902, **35**, 4302 ; 1903, **36**, 4026), Curtius (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1907, (ii) 76), Borsche (*Ber.*, 1921, **51B**, 660) and others have prepared derivatives of benztriazoles by different methods, but none seems to have found out a general way of synthesis of these derivatives. The present work is the outcome of an investigation undertaken in connection with the steric effect of chromophoric superposition on colour, which has been described in a separate communication. In connection with that investigation it was found that though *o*-nitro-azobenzene is very easily reduced to *o*-amino-azobenzene by alcoholic ammonium sulphide in normal manner, yet when *o*-nitro-benzene-azophenol (II) was similarly treated, instead of yielding the expected *o*-amino-benzene-azophenol, it gave an altogether different product which did not contain an amino group. On careful examination it was found that the product thus obtained was 2-(4'-hydroxyphenyl)-1 : 2 : 3-benztriazole (III).

I.

II.

III.

It was then thought that the reactive hydroxy group in the *o*-nitrobenzene-azophenol had probably something to do in bringing about this peculiar reaction, and accordingly it was methylated and the reaction tried again. In this case also the same thing happened and the product was found to be 2-(4'-methoxy-phenyl)-1:2:3-benzotriazole. So the reactivity of the hydroxy group in this connection was out of question. It was then thought that probably the weight of the substituent on the benzene nucleus containing the hydroxy group and not the reactivity of the latter was really responsible for this peculiar reaction, and accordingly an azo-dyestuff was prepared from diazotised aniline and *m*-nitraniline, which did not contain any substituent in the said benzene nucleus (IV, R'=NH₂, R=H). But when this substance was reduced with alcoholic ammonium sulphide, again a triazole derivative, namely, 5-amino-2-phenyl-1:2:3-benzotriazole (VII, R=H, R'=NH₂) formed.

So the conclusion that can be derived from the results of these experiments is that though *o*-nitro-azobenzene undergoes reduction by ammonium sulphide, in a normal manner, to *o*-amino-azo-benzene, yet as soon as a substituent is introduced in any of the two benzene nuclei, the two latter are brought nearer to each other in space, with the result that the reduction takes a different course and a derivative of benzotriazole is formed. The reaction probably undergoes the following course :

In (V), the effect of substituent R or R' is to bring the two benzene nuclei nearer to each other, so that the intermediate—NHOH group which is formed in course of reduction of the nitro group at once reacts with the hydrazo group which is also simultaneously formed by reduction of the azo group, with the result that a

dihydro benztriazole (VI) is formed, which spontaneously loses hydrogen and gets transformed into benztriazole (VII).

That the compounds described in this paper are real triazole derivatives was proved beyond doubt by oxidising 2-(4'-hydroxyphenyl)-1:2:3-benztriazole (III) with potassium permanganate in alkaline solution whereby triazole-dicarboxylic acid (VIII) was obtained, which was found to be identical with the acid obtained by Bladin (*Ber.*, 1893, 26, 545) on oxidation of methyl-benztriazole.

EXPERIMENTAL.

In the following series of experiments, *o*-nitraniline was first diazotised and coupled with various phenols and amino compounds in the usual manner. The azo-dyestuffs thus obtained were then treated with aqueous or alcoholic ammonium sulphide under suitable conditions whereby the azo compound was rapidly reduced and the corresponding benztriazole derivative obtained in very good, sometimes in almost quantitative yield.

2-(4'-Hydroxy-phenyl)-1:2:3-benztriazole.—Prepared from *o*-nitrobenzene-azophenol. Colourless silky needles from alcohol, m.p. 231°. (Found : N, 19.9. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{ON}_3$ requires N, 19.9 per cent.).

2-(4'-Methoxy-phenyl)-1:2:3-benztriazole.—Obtained from *o*-nitrobenzene-azophenol by first methylation with dimethyl sulphate in sodium hydroxide solution to *o*-nitrobenzene-azoanisole (yellow needles, m.p. 71°) and then reducing the latter with alcoholic ammonium sulphide. Colourless glistening plates from alcohol, melting at 138°. (Found : N, 18.5. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{11}\text{ON}_3$ requires N, 18.7 per cent.).

2-(2':4'-Dihydroxy-phenyl)-1:2:3-benztriazole.—Prepared from *o*-nitrobenzene-azoresorcinol (red powder, m.p. 185°). Pale brown silky needles from acetic acid melting at 191°. (Found : N, 18.9. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{O}_2\text{N}_3$ requires N, 18.5 per cent.).

2-(4'-Hydroxy-naphthyl)-1:2:3-benztriazole.—From *o*-nitrobenzene-azo-*a*-naphthol (red powder, m.p. 236°). It crystallises from alcohol in light yellow needles melting at 201°. (Found : N, 15.7. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{11}\text{ON}_3$ requires N, 16.1 per cent.).

2-(2'-Hydroxy-naphthyl)-1:2:3-benzotriazole.—From *o*-nitro-benzene-azo- β -naphthol (orange powder, m.p. 127°). Light brown needles from alcohol melting at 119°. Found: N, 16.5. $C_{15}H_{11}ON_3$, requires N, 16.1 per cent.).

2-(3'-Carboxy-4'-hydroxyphenyl)-1:2:3-benzotriazole.—From *o*-nitro-benzene-azo-salicylic acid (reddish brown powder, m.p. 217°). Colourless needles from alcohol, melting at 300°. (Found: N, 16.6. $C_{13}H_9O_3N_3$, requires N, 16.5 per cent.).

2-(3'-Carboxy-4'-hydroxy-naphthyl)-1:2:3-benzotriazole.—From *o*-nitrobenzene-azo- α -oxynaphthoic acid (purple powder, m.p. 168°). It crystallised from glacial acetic acid in light grey needles melting at 189°. (Found: N, 13.6. $C_{17}H_{11}O_3N_3$, requires N, 13.8 per cent.).

2-(4'-Carboxy-3'-hydroxy-phenyl)-1:2:3-benzotriazole.—From *o*-nitrobenzene-azo- β -oxynaphthoic acid (red powder, m.p. 247°). It crystallised from alcohol in colourless silky needles melting at 109°. (Found: N, 13.6. $C_{13}H_{11}O_3N_3$, requires N, 13.8 per cent.).

2-(2':3':4'-Trihydroxy-6'-carboxy-phenyl)-1:2:3-benzotriazole.—From *o*-nitrobenzene-azo-gallic acid (brown powder, m.p. 111°). The substance could not be crystallised. It was precipitated from alcohol as a yellow powder melting at 191°. (Found: N, 13.9. $C_{13}H_9O_5N_3$, requires N, 14.6 per cent.).

2-(4'-Hydroxy-3'-aldehydo-phenyl)-1:2:3-benzotriazole.—From *o*-nitrobenzene-azo-salicylaldehyde (brown needles, m.p. 148°). It crystallised from alcohol in glistening yellowish white needles, m.p. 132°. (Found: N, 17.4. $C_{13}H_9O_3N_3$, requires N, 17.6 per cent.).

2-(4'-Aminophenyl)-1:2:3-benzotriazole.—From *o*-nitrobenzene-azo-aniline (bright red needles, m.p. 195°). The substance crystallised from dilute alcohol in light yellow silky needles melting at 135°. (Found: N, 26.9. $C_{12}H_{10}N_4$, requires N, 26.6 per cent.).

The above substance on diazotising and boiling with water was converted into another substance melting at 231°, which was found to be identical with 2-(4'-hydroxy-phenyl)-1:2:3-benzotriazole already described.¹

2-(4'-Dimethylamino-phenyl)-1:2:3-benzotriazole.—From *o*-nitrobenzene-azo-dimethylaniline (red needles, m.p. 131°). Pale yellow needles from alcohol, melting at 187°. (Found: N, 23.1. $C_{14}H_{14}N_4$, requires N, 23.5 per cent.).

5-Amino-2-phenyl-1:2:3-benzotriazole.—Prepared from benzene-azo-*m*-nitraniline (orange needles, m.p. 121°) by reduction with

ammonium sulphide. It crystallised from alcohol in yellowish white shining plates melting at 182°. (Found: N, 25.9. $C_{11}H_{10}N_4$ requires N, 26.6 per cent.).

5-Amino-2-(4'-sulpho-phenyl)-1:2:3-benzotriazole.—Prepared from *p*-sulpho-benzene-azo-*m*-nitraniline (orange powder) by reduction with ammonium sulphide. It crystallised from glacial acetic acid in pale yellow silky needles. (Found: N, 18.9. $C_{11}H_{10}O_2N_4S$ requires N, 18.9 per cent.).

5-Amino-2-naphthyl-1:2:3-benzotriazole.—From 1-naphthalene-4-azo-nitraniline (orange needles, m.p. 138°) by reduction with ammonium sulphide. Yellow needles from alcohol, melting at 169°. (Found: N, 21.1. $C_{16}H_{11}N_4$ requires N, 21.5 per cent.).

5-Amino-2-(2'-naphthyl)-1:2:3-benzotriazole.—From naphthalene-2-azo-*m*-nitraniline (red powder, m.p. 169°) by reduction with ammonium sulphide. It could not be crystallised. It was obtained from alcohol in the form of a light brown powder, m.p. 114°. (Found: N, 21.4. $C_{16}H_{11}N_4$ requires N, 21.5 per cent.).

Oxidation of 2-(4'-Hydroxyphenyl)-1:2:3-benzotriazole.

Five gm. of the above substance were dissolved in the requisite quantity of dilute sodium hydroxide and treated with a 5% solution of potassium permanganate in the cold until the latter was no longer decolorised. The precipitated manganese dioxide was filtered off and the filtrate evaporated to a small volume after neutralisation with dilute sulphuric acid. The liquid was then rendered strongly acid with dilute sulphuric acid when a crystalline precipitate was formed. The latter was filtered off and was identified to be triazole-dicarboxylic acid.

